

1 **APOBEC3F is differentially expressed in glioblastoma.**

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6 Glioblastoma is difficult to treat and patients are often provided poor prognosis (1), indicating a
7 requirement for therapeutic target identification and drug development. Differentially expressed genes
8 represent by definition among the most promising targets for the development of novel chemotherapies (2,
9 3). We predict therapeutic index is intrinsically linked to differential expression which can be
10 comprehensively and blindly determined using whole transcriptome data, further limiting toxicity by
11 design (4). We mined published and public microarray and RNA-sequencing data (5, 6) to identify
12 differentially expressed gene products in glioblastoma by performing whole transcriptome gene expression
13 profiling. We found that the gene encoding the apolipoprotein B mRNA editing enzyme catalytic subunit
14 3F, APOBEC3F, was among those whose expression was most different in human glioblastoma tumors
15 when comparing total transcription between tumor and normal brain tissue. APOBEC3F expression levels
16 were significantly increased in glioblastoma tumors as compared to the non-transformed brain.
17 APOBEC3F function at the systems level was assessed by studying whole transcriptome transcriptional
18 co-regulation in the transformed brain. APOBEC3F is a target of interest for the treatment of
19 glioblastoma, as part of a rationally designed chemotherapeutic regimen that utilizes gene expression data
20 from patient tumors and healthy non-transformed tissues to maximize efficacy and safety and minimize
21 toxicity.

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26 Keywords: APOBEC3F, apolipoprotein B mRNA editing enzyme catalytic subunit 3F, glioblastoma,
27 systems biology of glioblastoma, targeted therapeutics in glioblastoma.

1 Brain cancer encompasses a spectrum of solid tumors that affect the brain including in children and
2 adults including medulloblastoma, neuroblastoma, and glioblastoma (7). Rational development of targeted
3 therapeutics to treat patients with glioblastoma can be supported by an enhanced understanding of
4 fundamental transcriptional differences that define the glioblastoma tumor. To discover genes associated
5 with glioblastoma in humans in an unbiased fashion and at the systems level, we compared total
6 transcription in the normal brain and in the glioblastoma tumor using published and public human
7 glioblastoma microarray and RNA-sequencing data (5, 6) to identify a molecular signature or fingerprint
8 of glioblastoma, among the most lethal and difficult to treat solid tumors affecting adults. We describe
9 here identification of a potential therapeutic target in glioblastoma based on quantitative whole
10 transcriptome methods.

11 **Methods**

12 We utilized microarray datasets GSE116520 (5) and GSE184643 (6) for this differential gene
13 expression analysis of the brain cancer glioblastoma in humans using R-based computational methods
14 (GEO2R). GSE116520 was generated using Illumina HumanHT-12 V4.0 expression beadchip
15 technology; for this analysis, we used $n=8$ control brain tissue and $n=17$ glioblastoma tumors, and the
16 analysis was performed using platform GPL10558. GSE184643 was generated using Illumina NovaSeq
17 6000 (Homo sapiens) technology; for this analysis, we used $n=3$ control brain tissue and $n=3$ glioblastoma
18 tumors, and the analysis was performed using platform GPL24676. All tumors utilized for differential
19 gene expression analysis here were of the adenocarcinoma type. The Benjamini and Hochberg method of
20 p-value adjustment was used for ranking of differential expression but raw p-values were used to assess
21 statistical significance of global differential expression. Log-transformation of data was auto-detected, and
22 the NCBI generated category of platform annotation was used. SEEK was utilized for transcriptional
23 co-regulation studies (8).

24 **Results**

25 We harnessed the power of whole transcriptome technologies and cross-laboratory validation (5, 6)
26 to discover in an unbiased fashion and at the transcriptome level the most distinguishing gene expression
27 features of the human brain cancer glioblastoma.

28 APOBEC3F is differentially expressed in glioblastoma.

1. Primary tumors of the brain from humans with glioblastoma

$n=8$ normal brain tissues (human)

$n=17$ primary tumors (brain; human; glioblastoma)

ID	<i>p</i> -value	t	B	logFC	Gene	Rank	%DE
ILMN_2412172	4.16E-13	10.3871039	19.766822	0.7143941	APOBEC3F	190/47229	99.6

29 Through quantitative comparison of total transcription in normal brain tissues and glioblastoma
30 tumor tissue, we discovered differential expression of apolipoprotein B mRNA editing enzyme catalytic
31 subunit 3F, encoded by APOBEC3F in glioblastoma in humans (**Chart 1**). The expression of APOBEC3F
32 changed more than 99% of the human brain and brain tumor transcriptome when considering all
33 transcripts whose expression was measured - in this case, 47,229 transcripts (“Rank”). Note the negative
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fold-change indicating increased quantity of APOBEC3F messenger RNA in glioblastoma tumors, demonstrating up-regulation of APOBEC3F during transformation of the brain from normal brain tissue to glioblastoma.

2. Primary tumors of the brain from humans with brain cancer: glioblastoma.

$n=3$ normal brain tissues (human)

$n=3$ primary tumors (brain; human; glioblastoma)

ID	<i>p</i> -value	lfcSE	stat	log2FoldChange	Gene	Rank	%DE
200316	1.75E-05	0.488	-4.294774	-2.09533199	APOBEC3F	1223/19678	93.8

Through quantitative comparison of total transcription in normal brain tissues and glioblastoma tumors in a second RNA-sequencing dataset from independent investigators and a separate patient cohort, we validated differential expression of APOBEC3F in glioblastoma in humans (**Chart 2**). The expression of APOBEC3F here changed more than 90% of the human brain and brain tumor transcriptome when considering all transcripts whose expression was measured - in this case, 19,678 transcripts (“Rank”). Note the negative fold-change indicating increased quantity of APOBEC3F messenger RNA in glioblastoma tumors, demonstrating up-regulation of APOBEC3F during transformation of the brain from normal brain tissue to glioblastoma.

Thus, APOBEC3F is a gene whose differential expression defines the transcriptional landscape of the glioblastoma subtype in humans.

APOBEC3F transcriptional co-regulation.

Finally, we utilized a separate systems methodology that utilizes whole transcriptome data to provide insight into molecular function of a gene product by evaluating the transcriptional network within which it operates through identification of co-regulated gene partners.

In the transformed brain, APOBEC3F was transcriptionally co-regulated with APOBEC3C, APOBEC3G, IFI35, TNFRSF14, TNFRSF1A, and GSDMD.

1 Thus, blind comparative transcriptome analysis of glioblastomas revealed differential expression of
2 APOBEC3F as among the most significant transcriptional features of glioblastoma tumors; systems level
3 query into APOBEC3F molecular function across multiple tissues at the transcriptome level revealed its
4 co-regulation with APOBEC3C, APOBEC3G, IFI35, TNFRSF14, TNFRSF1A, and GSDMD.

4 **Discussion**

5 We found by mining published and public microarray and RNA-sequencing data (5, 6) that the
6 apolipoprotein B mRNA editing enzyme catalytic subunit 3F, APOBEC3F, was among the genes most
7 differentially expressed in the primary tumors of patients with glioblastoma; APOBEC3F was expressed at
8 significantly higher levels in glioblastoma tumors as compared to the brain. APOBEC3F is a target of
9 interest for rationally designed medical treatment of glioblastoma, a difficult to treat adult solid tumor.
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